

**GOAL Support guide
for librarians**

**Negotiating a Green
Open Access Policy**

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What will you find in this guide?

If you are considering contacting a publisher or a journal to propose a Green Open Access Policy, this is your guide. In it you will find information on:

- What (and how) to prepare before approaching a publisher with an offer.
- What to take into account when contacting a publisher.
- How to prepare a proposal for a Green Open Access Policy.
- What to do if your suggestion is accepted and the publisher adopts a Green Open Access policy.

How is this guide organised?

The support guide for negotiations is divided into four chapters and an addenda:

1. Preparing a negotiation	4
2. Contacting a publisher or an editor	10
3. Negotiating with the publisher/editor	12
4. Final step: Adding the policy to the GOAL database	16
5. Addenda	
a. <u>Helpful links</u>	17
b. <u>Appendix: Quick negotiation guide</u>	19
c. <u>Appendix: Green OA Policy templates in English, French and German</u>	20

In each chapter you will find suggestions and useful links leading to further information. These include the quick support guide, the Green Open Access Policy templates in different languages and the link to the GOAL database.

Who is behind this guide?

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What is the background to this guide?

The information provided in this support guide is based on the experiences collected during the project **GOAL - Unlocking the Green Open Access Potential** (<https://opengoal.ch/>). Running from January 2022 to December 2024, GOAL has contacted over 100 journals to propose and develop Green Open Access policies based on dialogue between academic librarians and journal editors. The results are recorded in the GOAL database developed during the project, which is openly available at <https://goal.zhaw.ch/home>

GOAL is a project co-funded by swissuniversities and developed by a team led by the university library of the ZHAW Zurich University of Applied Sciences in close cooperation with members of the university libraries of the University of Applied Sciences of Lucerne (HSLU), the University of Applied Sciences and Arts Northwestern Switzerland (FHNW), the Zurich University of the Arts (ZHdK) and the University of Teacher Education of Fribourg (HEP | PH FR).

In addition to the GOAL team, a Sounding Board consisting of twelve other Swiss academic institutions (eight universities of teacher education and four universities of applied sciences) provides support and advice on an ad hoc basis. Legal advice is also provided by CCdigitallaw, the national Competence Center in Digital Law that supports Swiss Higher Education Institutions in dealing with legal questions related to the digitization process and the use of new media and technologies. (<https://www.ccdigitallaw.ch/>).

This support guide is an outcome of the GOAL project, which is carried out by the following partner institutions:

Zürcher Hochschule
für Angewandte Wissenschaften

HSLU Hochschule
Luzern

n w Fachhochschule
Nordwestschweiz

z hdk
Zürcher Hochschule der Künste
Zürich University of the Arts

HEP | PH FR

GOAL is a project co-funded by
swissuniversities

What are the general recommendations?

- Book time in your agenda
 - Negotiations take time: First, determine whether it is worthwhile to initiate one.
- Be patient
 - For most publishers/editors, adopting a green Open Access policy is a big step. The email exchange or meetings may be followed by days or weeks of waiting for a response.
- Be persistent
 - Avoid being too assertive, but if a significant amount of time passes without a response, follow up politely. Editors and publishers are often very busy, so you may need to gently remind them of the importance of an Open Access policy to them.
- Do not forget the big picture
 - Negotiations are resource-intensive for publishers and librarians. Negotiate archiving rights for all authors, not just those working at your institution. In this way, the workload can be shared between libraries and negotiations can be scaled up for smaller publishers and journals.

Chapter 1: Preparing for a negotiation

You have identified a journal that is relevant to authors working at your institution and that does not yet have an Open Access policy. There are two possibilities:

- You are already in contact with the journal and have established a connection with someone there.
- You have not yet established contact with the journal.

If you already are in contact with the journal, we recommend using the [quick guide](#) at the end of this document or downloading the copy published on Zenodo with the following DOI: [10.5281/zenodo.14512858](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14512858).

If you have not yet been in contact with the journal, we suggest reading further.

To prepare for a negotiation, there are a number of steps we suggest you take:

1. Gather information about the journal: This will help you get an idea of what a potentially successful offer might look like.
2. Prepare a concrete proposal: This will help to speed things up

Collecting information about the journal

The following checklist will help you to organise the information:

The kind of journal

- Is the journal scholarly or practice-oriented?
- Who is the target audience? Professionals, researchers, general public?
- How frequently does it publish?
- Does it publish in one or several languages?

The business model

- Who is behind the journal? An association, a private publisher, a higher education institution, a public administration?
- What is the business model?
 - Is it for free on the internet, does it have a subscription model, is it supported by membership fees?
 - Does it have paid advertising inside?

Chapter 1: Preparing for a negotiation

The academic relevance in numbers

- Check the number of articles and/or metadata in your university bibliography over the last few years. How many articles are currently in the university bibliography of your institution? How does this compare to the total number of articles published in each issue?

The journal, its layout, and resources

- Does it have a valid ISSN? (<https://portal.issn.org/>)
- Does it use DOIs?
- Does it use third-party materials such as images or graphics?
 - Take into account that professional magazines and practice-oriented journals usually use third-party content (mostly images) that cannot be licensed under a creative commons (cc) license. The images might not be relevant to the content of the article but are relevant to the journal's layout as a whole.
 - In many cases they might also contain advertisements.
- How is it published? Is it available in print, online and in print, or online only?
- What kind of article version could they deliver to the author or perhaps even to the library?
 - In what kind of format?
- Which bibliographic metadata is provided by the publisher or by bibliographic databases for articles?
 - Is it machine-readable?
- Are full texts of the journal already freely accessible through digitalization (e.g. in E-Periodica)?

The people behind the journal

- Who are the editors?
 - Are they related to or affiliated with a higher education institution?
 - If so, do they know about Open Access?
- Is there an editorial board?
 - Are there any members from your institution who you could contact for advice, support or negotiation?

Chapter 1: Preparing for a negotiation

Preparing an offer

Now that you know more about the journal, you can prepare a proposal. It should meet the interests of the authors and the academic libraries, while taking into account the interests, possibilities and capabilities of the journal/publisher.

We recommend that you prepare a specific proposal for three reasons:

- It sets the framework for the discussion.
- It clarifies your goals.
- It saves time: Many journals have limited resources, and providing a concrete offer facilitates a quicker decision-making.

Steps

- **Define your objectives (minimum - maximum goals)**
 - Identify the most realistic best option.
 - Determine the minimum requirements for the journal to be Open Access? (You can refer to examples like [this one](#) in the GOAL database).
- **Identify a ZOPA (Zone of Possible Agreement)**
 - What kind of version could the journal accept? Preprint, postprint, published version?
 - Check the use of images and the image rights.
 - Is it possible to accept a version without the images? Are they just for illustrative purposes or do they provide information that is not conveyed in the text key?
 - In what format can the publisher deliver the article (e. g. PDF, Word)?
 - Where can you find the article(s)?
 - Can the journal send a copy to the author?
 - Can it also send a copy to the author's library?
 - Can the article be downloaded from the website?

Chapter 1: Preparing for a negotiation

- Time embargo
 - Ideally, there should be no embargo: The Plan S (<https://www.coalition-s.org/>) and the Revised National Strategy do not foresee embargoes (<https://www.swissuniversities.ch/en/topics/open-science/open-access/national-strategy>).
 - If the publisher insists on an embargo, try to convince her/him to opt for a short one (3 or 6 months).
 - You can suggest to have an embargo that holds until the next issue of the journal is published.
- Self-archiving rights for libraries: Is it possible to include the following clause?
 - “In case of articles from authors affiliated with a Swiss Higher education institution at the time of publication the publisher xyz guarantees the respective Swiss Higher education institution the non-exclusive right to deposit a copy of the article as defined in the terms and conditions of this policy in its institution specific Open Access repository”.
- If the ZOPA points towards a restrictive policy, consider proposing the following clause:
 - “If the article was written as part of a project whose sponsor (e.g. SNSF) requires a different publication policy, this can be granted after consultation with the editors.”
 - Note: The clause would allow the journal to adopt a more restrictive Green Open Access policy in general, while remaining attractive to authors whose articles are the result of third-party-funded research.

Prepare a BATNA (Best Alternative To a Negotiated Agreement)

- A BATNA is the most advantageous alternative course of action you can take if the negotiation fails and no agreement can be reached.

Chapter 1: Preparing for a negotiation

- **Prepare a policy proposal**

- You can use the GOAL Green Open Access Policy Templates for this. You will find them at the end of this guide or as separate documents in Zenodo:

- English version: [10.5281/zenodo.13834305](https://zenodo.org/record/13834305)
- French version: [10.5281/zenodo.13844144](https://zenodo.org/record/13844144)
- German version: [10.5281/zenodo.13844164](https://zenodo.org/record/13844164)

- Prepare also a short alternative version.

- Many editorial boards with little experience on Open Access might feel overwhelmed by a long policy. A short clause can be a solution for them:
 - It should be a short sentence that the publisher/editor might be ready to accept and add to the journal's imprint, author guidelines...
 - You can find examples of very short Open Access guidelines in the GOAL database.

- **Write down how the policy will be implemented**

- Make some notes explaining how the policy will work in practice. Focus particularly on what it will mean for the journal.
 - A policy that is in databases such as the GOAL database leads to less individual requests regarding self-archiving.
 - Authors should be informed and provided with a copy of their article for republication.
 - Suggest how and where the policy can be published.

Chapter 1: Preparing for a negotiation

- **Build a rationale**

- Prepare some arguments to explain why a Green Open Access policy is beneficial for the journal.
 - Do this based on the information you have collected about the journal. For example:
 - Check the business model: Small private publishers may have a different approach than journals published by associations. Journals published by public institutions (e.g. a canton) will also have a different approach.
 - Check the number of issues and the number of articles per issue: Journals that have several issues per year and many articles per issue are in need of a different approach than journals that are only published once or twice.
 - You can adapt the arguments we have collected during the project. A Green Open Access policy helps the journal by:
 - Making it more attractive to authors from academic institutions.
 - It increases the discoverability and visibility of the journal at no cost:
 - Articles in institutional repositories always contain information about the journal.
 - The institutional repositories are used by major online search engines such as Google Scholar and BASE (Bielefeld Academic Search Engine - <https://www.base-search.net/>).
 - Other authors and students (i.e., potential future readers and/or authors) at academic institutions can get a glimpse of the journal
 - If the version of record can be uploaded to the repository, the work done by the publisher becomes more visible.
 - In the long run, it saves time:
 - No more individual requests from authors or libraries regarding self-archiving.
 - The workflow is simple and can be planned in advance.
 - The communication with authors and/or libraries can be standardised in advance by preparing a short text block for emailing authors or libraries.

Chapter 2: Establish contact

Once you have prepared your proposal, it is time to decide how you will contact the journal.

- If you have had recent contact with the journal/publisher, use the contact you know. You have already built up trust and you have someone who will listen to you and give you initial responses.
- If you are currently in contact with the journal/publisher
 - See if there is an opportunity to introduce the topic during your email exchange or conversation.
 - For example, if you are contacting them to request permission to upload individual articles to your repository, you could mention that adopting a Green Open Access policy would streamline the process and save time for everyone involved.
- If you have not yet had contact, decide whether to write or call.

Phone calls / video calls

Arguments in favour of phone calls

- Stronger personal contact, as calls are more binding.
- Provide the opportunity to collect more information.
- Misunderstandings or questions can be immediately solved during the call.
- You can always offer a second meeting to discuss the details: Nowadays a video call usually follows.

Best practice for phone calls / video calls

- Prepare two or three sentences to introduce yourself and the reason for the call (name, institution, importance of the journal, relevance of Open Access).
- End the call by summarising the next steps (who will do what and when).
- After the call, it is helpful to send a short email thanking them for their time.
 - Include in the email the tasks, further information and, if agreed, a draft of the policy that they can revise at the journal. The document with the draft could also include tailored arguments for adopting a Green Open Access policy (use the information you have gathered previously).

Chapter 2: Establish contact

E-mail

- Keep it short: be as clear as possible.
- Use a clear title.
- Introduce yourself briefly and explain why you are contacting them
 - Why their journal is important to your library and to authors working in academic institutions.
 - Add two or three (short) reasons why a policy might benefit them. Tailor your arguments to the information you have gathered.
- Finish offering them one of the following:
 - Set up an online meeting or phone call (30 to 40 minutes is recommended) to further explain the idea and answer any questions they may have.
 - Send them a draft Open Access policy tailored to their journal for them to review.
- Pay attention to elements that build trust:
 - Use an institutional account
 - Use a signature with contact details

Keep the following in mind

- It may take some time to get a response.
- You may need to send the email again.

Chapter 3: Negotiate and check the implementation

Each negotiation is different. In this section we offer a list of lessons learned during the GOAL project.

- Be patient:
 - The actual negotiation time may be short, but the waiting time can be days or even weeks.
- Be persistent:
 - If you have not heard from the editor or publisher for a while, consider sending a polite follow-up. A brief email reminding them of your request and expressing your eagerness to hear from the can be effective.
- End the meetings by summarising the following:
 - Things you have agreed on
 - Next steps: Who does what and when
- It is a good idea to send an email summarising the decisions. This way both parties have a written reminder of what was decided and when.
- In general terms, academic libraries and librarians enjoy social trust and respect. This means that:
 - Most publishers/editors will be ready to listen to you (but not for long).
 - It also means that, as you are the one making the proposal, they will expect you to know more about the subject than they do. You do not need to be an expert in legal matters, but you should be prepared to explain a wide range of things quickly.
 - It is of help to have concrete examples at hand or easy materials explaining the different “roads” of Open Access in general and the green one in particular.

Chapter 3: Negotiate and check the implementation

Further experiences

In the following list you will find questions we faced:

- What is Open Access and why is it important (to them)?
- Why is your offer good for them? (see the list of arguments)
- How many articles are we talking about?
 - See the information from the preliminary work to prepare the negotiation.
- What do you (i. e. the library) get out of it?
 - It is important to clarify that academic libraries operate as non-profit organizations. We are not competitors; rather, we serve as a vital link between journals and a wide range of potential readers.

- What is an institutional repository?
 - How does it work?
 - It is advisable to prepare an example beforehand (if possible from their journal)
 - What kind of information can you find in the repository?
 - They will usually want to know if the journal title appears in the repository entry and, in case of having a version of the article, if links to the original publication on the publisher's website can be added.

- What are they expected to do?
 - What should they decide?
 - Where should the Green Open Access Policy be published? (on their website and in the GOAL database)

- What does a Green Open Access policy mean in practice?
 - How does it affect the communication with authors?
 - How does it affects the communication with academic libraries?

Chapter 3: Negotiate and check the implementation

Further experiences (continuation)

- Why can images be a problem?
 - Depending on the journal, image rights can be a problem for a secondary publication policy (a Green Open Access policy) with a CC-license. Many editors/publishers won't think of it at the outset, so it's important that you do.
- Possible solutions to the image rights problem
 - Low-threshold:
 - Legally: A restrictive license
 - Note: This is a pragmatic solution for small publishers with limited resources. It allows you to bring them into basic Open Access and leaves the door open for future developments.
 - More developed options:
 - Organisationally:
 - By asking authors to only use third-party images that are licensed under a CC-license.
 - In the case of the publisher: By using images with CC-licenses.
 - Technically:
 - By providing a version without images (if they are not essential to the article).
 - By blacking them out afterwards and before the article is uploaded to the repository. Take into consideration that it will be most likely librarians who will have to take over this task.

Chapter 3: Negotiate and check the implementation

If the editor/publisher is convinced and agrees to adopt a Green Open Access policy, you are *almost* there.

The transition from deciding to adopt a Green Open Access policy to actually publishing it on the web and informing authors can be significant for most publishers and editors. Even if they are, or appear to be, convinced of its value, it may take some time and several more emails before the policy is implemented. Some common reasons for this delay include:

- Limited importance of Open Access to their day-to-day business *and* limited workforce regarding the update of the website.
 - In many cases, small publishers or journals do not update their websites regularly. During the intervals between updates, they may overlook the importance of Open Access.
 - This is one of the reasons why publishers/editors may welcome a concrete proposal from the outset, including a suggestion as to where the policy should be publicised. It means less work.
 - If you fear this might happen, we suggest that you make it part of the negotiation. When you summarise who does what and when, you can include that if after a while they have not informed you about the publication of the policy, you will come back and ask them.
- Open Access means something fundamentally new: the fear of losing subscribers or having fewer visitors may be very strong, even if they see the positive potential of a Green Open Access policy.
 - You might try to counter this by showing examples of similar journals/publishers who already have an Open Access policy. The GOAL database can be helpful in finding examples.
- They still have doubts about specific aspects, though they have not expressed them openly.
 - Check with them if this is the case and offer your assistance. A restrictive policy is better than no policy at all.
- They may be in favour of having a policy, but they do not want to have it on their website.
 - No problem! All you need is their permission to add it to the GOAL database. Send us the information and we will publish the policy.

Chapter 4: Add the policy to the GOAL database

If the policy is published (or if you get the permission to add it to the GOAL database), please let us know. We will be happy to add the information. You can use the contact form in our database to reach us: <https://goal.zhaw.ch/info/contact>

Since you have come this far, you know the case much better than we do. It would be very helpful to us if you could provide us with the following information when informing about the new policy:

- Publisher
- URL of the publisher
- Title of the journal
- URL of the journal
- ISSN (if available)
- Link to the policy (or a copy of the policy if it is not on the website but can be published)

With this information at hand we can quickly retrieve the rest we need for the inclusion in the database.

Addenda: Helpful links

Negotiating a Green Open Access policy may present unexpected questions that are not addressed in detail in this guide. The following links can be of help to answer some of them.

Where to submit the policy

- GOAL-database: <https://goal.zhaw.ch/info/contact>
- Open policy finder (formerly Sherpa/Romeo): <https://openpolicyfinder.jisc.ac.uk>
 - In exceptional cases, the journal might comply with all the requisites for its inclusion in the Open policy finder database. If this is the case, we recommend you inform the publisher/editor and suggest they allow you to send the information to Sherpa/Romeo.

Information about Open Access

- oa-network: The Open-Access-Network offers lots of information around Open Access
 - Information classified by topics: From basic questions to legal situation in different countries: <https://open-access.network/en/information>
 - Glossary: <https://open-access.network/en/information/glossary>
- swissuniversities Open Access strategy:
 - General information:
 - <https://www.swissuniversities.ch/themen/digitalisierung/open-education-digital-competencies>
 - The revised strategy:
 - Swissuniversities. *Swiss National Open Access Strategy. Revised in 2024*. Bern, Swissuniversities, 2024.
 - https://www.swissuniversities.ch/fileadmin/swissuniversities/Dokument_e/Hochschulpolitik/Open_Access/Swiss-National-Open-Access-Strategy-2024-en.pdf
- Swiss National Science Fond, Open Access
 - <https://oa100.snf.ch/en/home-en/>

Addenda: Helpful links

More materials from the GOAL project

- GOAL-Community on Zenodo:
 - The GOAL project has produced several outcomes that might be of use to you. This guide and the database are two of them. The rest you will find in our GOAL-Community on Zenodo.
 - <https://zenodo.org/communities/goal/>

Information useful for editors

- PLATO-Project:
 - PLATO - Platinum Open Access Funding is a project (2022-2024) also co-funded by swissuniversities: <https://www.openscience.uzh.ch/en/scholarly-publishing-and-open-access/publishing-at-uzh/scholar-led-publishing/plato.html>
 - Focused on expanding Diamond Open Access among journals, the PLATO team prepared a useful guide for journal editors, containing information on how to improve the journal and eventually make it Diamond:
 - PLATO Project (ed.) (no date) *Information for editors of Diamond Open Access Journals*, UZH - Open Science. Available at: <https://www.openscience.uzh.ch/en/scholarly-publishing-and-open-access/publishing-at-uzh/scholar-led-publishing/plato/info.html> (Accessed: 07 November 2024).
 - The guide contains information about the usefulness of ISSN or DOI

Information useful for authors / creators

- OS-ADM-Guidelines
 - OS-ADM - Open Science for Arts, Design and Music, is another swissuniversities co-funded project that aims to expand Open Science and Open Access among authors and creators. Within the project, a comprehensive guideline has been developed and published.
 - Chiara Somajni, Erzsébet Tóth-Czifra, Chiara Barbieri, Suzanna Marazza and Iolanda Pensa, *Open Science for Arts, Design and Music*, SUPSI, 2024. Available at: https://meta.wikimedia.org/wiki/Open_Science_for_Arts,_Design_and_Music/O_S-ADM_Guidelines (Accessed: 07 November 2024).

1 Preparing the proposal I - Collecting information

Make explicit to yourself what you know and what you need to know about the journal and the publisher.

- If you need help in this task, use the long version of this support guide (DOI: [10.5281/zenodo.14512487](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14512487)).

Preparing the proposal II - Prepare an offer - Step 1 **2**

Based on your findings during the preparation, draft a policy that best fits the needs of the publisher from your perspective. Use our policy templates as a starting point:

- English Version: [10.5281/zenodo.13834305](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13834305)
- French Version: [10.5281/zenodo.13844144](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13844144)
- German Version: [10.5281/zenodo.13844164](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13844164)

3 Preparing the proposal III - Prepare an offer - Step 2

- Prepare arguments to convince the publisher: Why should they adopt a Green Open Access Policy?
 - Think from the perspective of the publisher.
 - You can find a list of helpful questions in our long support guide.

- Prepare also a BATNA (Best Alternative to Negotiated Agreement): For example, a short sentence that could be added to the journal imprint.

Negotiate - Step 1 - Making contact **4**

- Decide in advance how to contact the editor / publisher
- Contact a representative of the journal who is most likely in a position to decide on a self-archiving policy.
- Make up an appointment for a video-call or even a personal meeting.

5 Negotiate - Step 2 - Present your offer & look for an agreement

- Be concise:
 - Why do you suggest a policy? Explain the benefits for the journal.
 - How could it look like?
 - How can the policy be implemented?
 - Prepare a list of to dos for the publisher, libraries and authors.
 - Where can they publish the policy on their website?
 - Where can it be ingested (the GOAL database)?
- Close every meeting with a short summary of the next steps agreed on.
- Agree on deadlines.
- Take into account:
 - You might have to meet several times.
 - You might have to offer alternatives to your first offer.
 - It might take time for the editor or the editorial board to decide.

Make the results known: the GOAL Database **6**

- Once you have reached an agreement and the policy is publicly available, submit it to the GOAL-Database using the feedback form:
 - <https://goal.zhaw.ch/info/contact>

How to use this template:

You can configure a Green Open Access Policy tailored to your needs by combining the different elements of this template. The column on the left side contains the most open options for a policy. The central column contains standardised formulations that apply to all possible policies. If you want to add restrictions of some kind, then simply choose among the diverse options from the column on the right side.

Most open version

Standard text

Options

Open Access promotes the visibility of publications. This is in the interest of both authors and publishers and is in line with the requirements of the Swiss universities and the national Open Access strategy of swissuniversities and the SNSF

have the right to republish the

final version of their article (fully copyedited, typeset and formatted copy of the manuscript as published)

accepted manuscript (final draft of the journal article after it has been reviewed and accepted for publication, but before it has been typeset and formatted by the journal)

in any format they like

as a PDF

openly available online and free from payment

on any website and/or a repository

(Pick one)

- in the repository of their choice, on their personal homepage as well as social network
- via a non-commercial repository
- via a non-commercial subject repository
- via a non-commercial institutional repository

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- Creative Commons licence [CC BY-NC-ND 4.0](#) (redistribution, only non-commercial use with attribution and proper citation, unadapted form only).
- Compliance with the publisher **xyz** conditions that grant usage rights in accordance with the [Swiss copyright law](#).

The article may be made accessible immediately upon publication.

(Pick one)

- The article may be made accessible after a 3 months embargo period after publication.
- The article may be made accessible after a 6 months embargo period after publication.
- The article may be made accessible after a 12 months embargo period after publication.
- The article may be made accessible after a 24 months embargo period after publication.

The original publication by the publisher including complete bibliographic information (e.g. article title, journal name, volume) must be mentioned in a clearly visible place

(Pick one)

- In addition, the DOI of the published article must be used to link to the publisher's publication.
- In addition, the URL of the published article on the journal's website must be indicated.

The publisher provides the author with a copy/version of his article for secondary publication.

The article can be downloaded from the website of the publisher for secondary publication by the author.

In case of articles from authors affiliated with a Swiss Higher education institution at the time of publication the publisher **xyz** guarantees the respective Swiss Higher education institution the non-exclusive right to deposit a copy of the article as defined in the terms and conditions of this policy in its institution specific Open Access repository.

The publisher provides the library with a copy/version of the articles affected for secondary publication.

- Articles can be downloaded from the website of the publisher for secondary publication by the library.
- (dismiss phrase if not applicable)

This policy affects articles published after ...

If you have questions regarding the template or the project GOAL, send us an email to [goal-project\[at\]zhaw.ch](mailto:goal-project[at]zhaw.ch). If the use of the policy template results in the development and implementation of an Open Access Policy, we are glad to incorporate it to the GOAL-Database. Visit us at <https://goal.zhaw.ch/home> and send us the new policy for incorporation by using the feedback form on the footer.

GREEN OPEN ACCESS POLICY TEMPLATE A do it yourself policy guideline © 2024 by Andres, Valérie; Brunner, Cornelia; Corredera Nilsson, Enrique; Flieg, Julia; Moritz, Andrea; Reymermier, Hélène; Trautwein, Clemens is licensed under CC BY-SA 4.0

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HSLU Hochschule Luzern

n w

Fachhochschule Nordwestschweiz

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Zürcher Hochschule der Künste
Zürich University of the Arts

GOAL is a project co-funded by
swissuniversities

Comment utiliser ce modèle :

Vous pouvez réaliser une politique Green Open Access adaptée à vos besoins en combinant les différents éléments de ce modèle. La colonne de gauche contient les options les plus ouvertes pour une politique. La colonne centrale contient des formulations standardisées qui s'appliquent à toutes les politiques possibles. Si vous souhaitez ajouter des restrictions de quelque nature que ce soit, choisissez simplement parmi les diverses options de la colonne de droite.

Modèle (meilleure version)

Texte standard

Options

L'Open Access améliore la visibilité des publications, dans l'intérêt des chercheur-e-s et des éditeur-trice-s, et en accord avec les exigences des universités suisses et de la stratégie nationale Open Access de Swissuniversities et le FNS.

Les auteur-e-s

Les auteur-e-s affilié-e-s à des institutions académiques suisses

ont le droit de republier

la version finale de leur article publié (copie conforme de leur manuscrit, tel qu'il a été publié)

le manuscrit accepté pour publication (brouillon final de l'article après qu'il ait été revu et accepté pour publication, mais avant qu'il soit édité et formaté par l'éditeur-trice)

dans le format qu'ils souhaitent (meilleure pratique : PDF)

en format PDF

et de le rendre disponible
en ligne, sans paiement

sur tout site internet
et/ou une archive

(Choisissez un type d'archive)

- dans l'archive de leur choix, sur leur page personnelle ou encore sur les réseaux sociaux
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- Conditions d'utilisation de l'éditrice xyz, qui sont en accord avec la [loi suisse sur le droit d'auteur](#).

L'article peut être rendu accessible immédiatement après sa publication.

(Choisissez une période d'embargo)

- L'article peut être rendu accessible après une période d'embargo de 3 mois après sa publication.
- L'article peut être rendu accessible après une période d'embargo de 6 mois après sa publication.
- L'article peut être rendu accessible après une période d'embargo de 12 mois après sa publication.
- L'article peut être rendu accessible après une période d'embargo de 24 mois après sa publication.

La publication originale de l'éditeur-trice, comprenant les informations bibliographiques complètes (titre de l'article, nom de la revue, volume) doit être mentionnée à une place clairement visible.

(Choisissez une option)

- En plus, le DOI de l'article publié doit être utilisé pour faire le lien avec la publication de l'éditeur-trice.
- En plus, l'URL de l'article publié sur le site internet de la revue doit être indiquée.

L'éditeur-trice fournit une copie/version de son article à l'auteur-e pour republication.

L'article peut être téléchargé par l'auteur-e depuis le site internet de l'éditeur-trice, pour une republication.

Dans le cas d'articles d'auteur-e-s affilié-e-s à une institution académique suisse au moment de la publication, l'éditeur-trice garantit à l'institution académique respective le droit non-exclusif de déposer une copie de l'article dans son archive institutionnelle Open Access spécifique, comme défini dans les termes et conditions de cette politique.

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- Les articles peuvent être téléchargés sur le site internet de l'éditeur-trice pour une republication par la bibliothèque
- (Supprimer la phrase si elle n'est pas applicable)

Cette politique concerne les articles publiés après...

Si vous avez des questions concernant le modèle ou le projet GOAL, envoyez-nous un courriel à [goal-project\[at\]zhaw.ch](mailto:goal-project[at]zhaw.ch)

Si l'utilisation du modèle de politique aboutit au développement et à la mise en œuvre d'une politique de libre accès, nous serons heureux de l'intégrer à la base de données GOAL. Rendez-nous visite sur <https://goal.zhaw.ch/home> et envoyez-nous la nouvelle politique pour intégration en utilisant le feedback formulaire en bas de page.

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Ce modèle est le résultat du projet GOAL, réalisé en collaboration avec les partenaires suivants.

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Wie Sie diese Vorlage verwenden:

Sie können eine Zweitveröffentlichungsrichtlinie entwerfen, die Ihren Bedürfnissen entspricht. Kombinieren Sie dafür die Elemente dieser Vorlage mit den Standardformulierungen in der Mitte. Diese werden ergänzt durch Elemente aus der linken oder rechten Spalte. Die linke Spalte enthält die optimale Version im Sinne des Open Access, die rechte Spalte restriktivere Optionen.

Optimale Version

Standardtext

Restriktive Version

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machen

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einem Repository

(Eine auswählen)

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Die Originalveröffentlichung des Verlags muss einschließlich der vollständigen bibliografischen Angaben (z. B. Titel des Artikels, Name der Zeitschrift, Band) an einer deutlich sichtbaren Stelle genannt werden.

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Bei Artikeln von Autorinnen und Autoren, die zum Zeitpunkt der Publikation einer Schweizer Hochschule angehören, garantiert der Verlag **xyz** der betreffenden Hochschule das nicht-exklusive Recht, eine Kopie des Artikels gemäss den Bedingungen dieser Policy in ihrem Open-Access-Repository zu hinterlegen.

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Diese Richtlinie betrifft Artikel ab den Publikationsdatum ...

Wenn Sie Fragen zur Vorlage oder zum Projekt GOAL haben, senden Sie uns eine E-Mail an [goal-project\[at\]zhaw.ch](mailto:goal-project[at]zhaw.ch)
Wenn die Verwendung der Richtlinienvorlage zur Entwicklung und Umsetzung einer Open-Access-Richtlinie führt, nehmen wir diese gerne in die GOAL-Datenbank auf. Besuchen Sie uns auf <https://goal.zhaw.ch/home> und senden Sie uns die neue Policy zur Aufnahme mit dem Feedback-Formular in der Fußzeile.

Diese Vorlage ist ein Ergebnis des Projekts GOAL, das von den folgenden Partnern durchgeführt wird

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